

VillageMath Educational Review

An International/Multidisciplinary Journal of
Network for Grassroots Science and Mathematics
Education (The VillageMath Network)

A publication of VillageMath Educational Services
(CAC RC: 4097888)

Volume 6, Issue 1

April, 2024

CODEN: VERIAU

Awareness and Utilization of Agricultural Information Resources for Improved Research Productivity of Agricultural Scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State

Adarju Abubakar ADAMU ¹, Solomon Achia UGANNEYA ², and
Victor OZOWA ²

^{1,2,3} Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10959690

Article History: Received 3rd April, 2024; Revised 10th April, 2024; Published 11th April, 2024.

Copyright © 2024 by Author(s) and The VillageMath Network

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

How to Cite this Article:

Adamu, A. A., Uganneya, S. A. & Ozowa, V. (2024). Awareness and Utilization of Agricultural Information Resources for Improved Research Productivity of Agricultural Scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State. *VillageMath Educational Review (VER)*, 6(1), 13-26.

<https://ngsme.villagemath.net/journals/ver/v6i1/adamu-uganneya-ozowa>

Abstract

This study investigated awareness and utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity of agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba library Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. The study was guided by five objectives and five research questions. The study adopted descriptive survey research design with a population of 216 agricultural scientists from the six agricultural colleges at Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi. The sample size for the study was 140 agricultural scientists from the different colleges and was determined through Taro Yamen sampling formula. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire structured and designed by the

researchers and titled Questionnaire on Awareness and Utilization of Agricultural Information Resources for Improved Research Productivity of Agricultural Scientists (QAUAIRIPAS). Out of the 140 copies of questionnaire distributed, 133 copies were retrieved and certified suitable for the study. Data collected was then analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation and presented in tables. The findings of the study revealed that agricultural scientists are aware and utilize agricultural information resources for improved research productivity at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi. The study also revealed that the utilization of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, improve the research productivity of agricultural scientists. The finding discovered that there are challenges encountered by agricultural scientists in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity and if these challenges are properly handled, it would go a long way in enhancing the utilization and thereby improving the research productivity of these agricultural scientists in agricultural institutions. Based on these findings, the researchers recommended among others that, both university management and the library should provide current agricultural information resources and allocate more space in the library for agricultural scientists to carry out their research activities.

Keywords: Agricultural Information Resources, Awareness, Research Productivity, Utilization, Agricultural Scientists

Introduction

One of the basic functions of every library is to make sure that information resources are readily available for the users to access at all times. Every library contains different information resources that are purposely organized to meet user's needs. A library serves as a vital and important channel, where information is acquired, processed and disseminated through the provision of appropriate information resources and services in various formats. According to Aina (2004), the library is a learning center because it provides materials that are needed for learning in all field to both students and staff of a particular institution. The library provides resources and services to support teaching and research and as well for extracurricular activities. When library users visit the library, it is expected that up-to-date information resources, particularly, agricultural information resources, are readily available for them as it will aid in effective teaching, learning and research.

Agricultural information resources constitute a range of materials and equipment organized in the field of agriculture by the library in order to meet the information needs of both intended and anticipated users in that field. Maidabino and Ladan (2015) refers to agricultural information resources as any information especially in agriculture that are organized in electronic format, audio visual or physical form or any information in hardware or software that makes possible the storage and use of agricultural information. Similarly, Okiki (2013) defined agricultural information resources to refer to print and electronic materials that could be sourced and accessed manually or electronically by users in agricultural field.

These resources include books, journals, theses, dissertations, technical reports and all related agricultural materials in print format and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and related electronic gadgets which store or provide information worldwide without any serious geographical barrier capable of satisfying the diverse

information needs of researchers in agriculture. Amidu and Akolo (2015) listed that agricultural information resources are usually displayed in the form of journals, maps, proceedings, abstracts, textbooks, encyclopedia, dictionaries, gazettes, past examination question papers, government publications, technical reports, student projects, CD ROM and so on. These information resources are the raw materials that Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library acquire and make available to meet the information needs of agricultural scientists for improved research productivity.

A library should be well equipped with current information resources so as to encourage users to patronize the library. Hanif, Zabed and Nasir (2007) asserts that, in order to satisfy the diverse information needs and interests of the user's community, the library collection must be adequately available and organized and be rich in terms of quantity, quality and currency. Francis Suleimanu Idachaba library is an academic library at Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, established in 1994, to provide information resources in the field of agriculture, sciences and engineering. The library has over 250,000 information resources in the field of agriculture at both main and college libraries that are readily available for agricultural scientists. More so, these information resources have helped in the improvement of the research productivity of agricultural scientists at Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi. Agricultural scientists on the other hand are researchers and practitioners in agriculture and related areas that are committed to sharing information and working together to solve agricultural problems. They include soil scientists, crop scientists, weed scientists, agricultural economists, agricultural engineers among others that are staff of Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi. These individuals are expected to have knowledge of and utilize information resources to solve agricultural problems through research and as a consequence, enhance food productivity of the nation (Uganneya, Ape & Ugbagir, 2013). Most times, Agricultural scientists show great willingness to utilize information resources to improve their research productivity but a lot of them may not be aware of the varieties of information resources. This problem may cause them inadequacy or not to properly utilize these resources for improved research productivity.

Awareness has to do with the ability to know of the existence of something. Awareness is knowledge about something that exists or understanding of a situation or subject at the present time based on information or experience (Suleiman, Vashistha, and Jimah, 2018). Awareness should be created to enlighten and encourage the utilization of information resources that are available for agricultural scientists as this will have positive impact and improve their research productivity. In creating awareness, the agricultural scientists will have idea of the various types of agricultural information resources available for their research productivity and there by utilizing these resources to improve research productivity especially at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba library Makurdi.

Different researchers have conducted researches to show the awareness and utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity. Eyiolorunsho and Eluwole (2017) in their study on awareness, accessibility and use of library resources in Nigeria discovered that university staff are highly aware of information resources in the library and these resources were also utilized by the faculty members for academic purpose. Their study also noted that university staff easily accessed print resources

than electronic resources and that the information resources were underutilized by the staff despite their high level of awareness and easy accessibility of the available resources. Onifade, Ogbuiyi and Omeluzor (2013) in their study found out that majority of the university students frequently utilized the library for research, to prepare for seminar presentation and to read news. Their study revealed that the frequently used information resources are textbooks, monograph resources, Journals, handbooks, manuals, theses and dissertations among others. Their study further revealed some of the challenges encountered by postgraduate students in using the library resources and services to include lack of time, insufficient internet access points, lack of library orientation, opening hours of the library, short duration of book loan, inadequate space in the library, obsolete books. Ifijeh, Ogbomo and Ifijeh (2018) in their study discovered that university lecturers made use of the resources and the frequently used information resources are textbooks, journals, encyclopedia, newspapers/magazines, dictionaries, e-books, e-map, and online dictionary. The findings also showed that utilization of library resources improves lecturer research productivity. The study noted some of the challenges encountered by lecturers in using library resources to include cost of publication, time pressure and deadline, students project and theses supervision, delay in implementation of promotion and entitlement, excess workload, attendance to lectures and seminar, inadequate research personnel for instrumentality and analysis and so on. Their study recommended that university management should ensure that required facility that ensure high level of utilization of library resources are adequately provided and work pressure should be reduced.

Similarly, Kutu and Olajide (2020) in their study revealed that there is high availability and utilization of information resources by academic staff in university in North Central Nigeria. Their study recommended that all academic libraries should ensure provision of adequate information resources to encourage maximum utilization. Hussaini, Vashitha and Jimah (2018) in their study revealed that the frequently used information resources are textbooks/e-books, journals/e-journals, newspapers/magazines and internet/computers. They further discovered that there is high level of awareness and utilization of information resources in the library. The researchers recommended that institutions should provide vibrant library stacked with library resources updated to meet up the information requirement of library users. Okiki (2013) reported findings that revealed there is availability of information resources but varies in all the federal universities. The result also revealed that the availability of information resources does not necessarily determine the research productivity of academic staff. Song and Abbas (2019) in their study of availability and utilization of electronic information resources for research activities in agricultural research institutes in Kaduna state, Nigeria revealed that there is availability of electronic information resources in agricultural research institutions. The study also discovered that most of the electronic information resources available are adequately utilized for research activities. The study established that availability and utilization of electronic information resources have significant relationship with enhancement of research activities. Therefore, the more users utilize electronic information resources, the better the development of their research activities. The work by Zainab (2011) also revealed that researchers who used varied method to keep themselves up to date with current research literature are highly productive. It was

discovered that inability to find relevant information and services, lack of information and not knowing how to choose relevant database are challenges encountered by researchers.

In the same vein, Ilo, Igbashal and Agoh (2019) in their study revealed that library information resources are available and are highly utilized for research productivity by agricultural scientists in agricultural institutions in Benue state. The study noted that the frequently used information resources are theses, dictionaries, manuals, textbooks, journals, handbooks among others. Ilo and Ozowa (2021) likewise revealed that there is availability of information resources and agricultural scientists' accesses and utilizes the resources for research productivity. Among the utilized information resources are atlas/maps, articles, journals, textbooks, theses, eBooks and so on. The study also revealed that challenges like irregular power supply, excessive library rules, poor network connectivity, inadequate relevant information resources in the library, poor indexing of information resources among others are mostly encountered by agricultural scientists in agricultural institutions in Benue State. It was then recommended that if the challenges are tackled properly, it would go a long way in enhancing the research productivity of agricultural scientists in agricultural institutions in Benue State. It is against this background that this study is determined to examine awareness and utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity of agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Libraries in agricultural institutions are established by government to provide current and relevant information resources for agricultural scientists in order to assist in their research productivity and solve research problems. These libraries are often well equipped and organized with up-to-date information resources so that the users will be able to access and retrieve needed information resources in no time. These libraries serve as research venues as it helps agricultural scientists to improve in the quality and quantity of their research productivity. Research productivity in a way determine the extent of awareness and utilization of the library and its information resources. This productivity translates to the amount of efforts put in by agricultural scientists in the utilization of information resources available in the libraries. If research productivity is low, that means the library is not well equipped or the resources are not fully utilized.

Literature relating to this study were scanty and few similar studies have been carried out on agricultural scientists but none has covered the Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State, to the best of knowledge of this researchers and this has created a gap that this study intend to fill. Therefore, the study intends to investigate awareness and utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity of agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate awareness and utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity of agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. To ascertain the extents of awareness of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity of agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State.
- ii. To find out the extent to which the utilization of agricultural information resources by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state improve their research productivity.
- iii. To determine how the utilization of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state improve the research productivity of agricultural scientists.
- iv. To find out the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity.
- v. To proffer solutions to the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

- i. To what extent is agricultural scientists aware of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state for improved research productivity?
- ii. To what extent do agricultural scientists utilize agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state for improved research productivity?
- iii. How does the utilization of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state improve the research productivity of agricultural scientists?
- iv. What are the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity?
- v. What are the solutions to the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity?

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design with a population of 216 agricultural scientists from the six agricultural colleges at Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 140 agricultural scientists from Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi and was determined through Taro Yamen sampling formula. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire structured and designed by the researchers and titled Questionnaire on Awareness and Utilization of Agricultural Information Resources for Improved Research Productivity of Agricultural Scientists (QAUAIRIRPAS). The questionnaire was distributed by the researchers and three other research assistants within the University, for easy retrieval. Out of the 140 copies of

questionnaire distributed, 133 copies were retrieved and certified suitable for the study. Data collected was then analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation and presented in tables.

Results and Discussion

Research Question One

To what extent is agricultural scientists aware of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state for improved research productivity?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the extent to which agricultural scientists are aware of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State for improved research productivity (N=133)

S/N	Item statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank	Decision
1	Textbooks	3.62	.80	3 rd	VHE
2	Journals	3.80	.49	1 st	VHE
3	Newspapers	2.05	1.14	9 th	LE
4	Magazine	2.71	1.22	7 th	HE
5	Encyclopedia	1.75	.89	11 th	LE
6	Handbooks	3.51	.78	4 th	VHE
7	Dictionaries	3.11	1.10	6 th	VHE
8	Manuals	3.05	.98	5 th	VHE
9	Atlas and Maps	1.77	1.12	10 th	LE
10	Theses and dissertations	3.75	.66	2 nd	VHE
11	Monographs	1.26	.66	12 th	LE
12	Bibliography	2.58	1.40	8 th	HE
Grand Mean and Decision		2.75	-		HE

Result in Table 1 shows the Mean and Mean and Standard Deviation on the extent to which agricultural scientists are aware of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state for improved research productivity. The finding revealed journals ($\bar{X} = 3.80$, $SD = .49$), Theses and dissertation ($\bar{X} = 3.75$, $SD = .66$), Textbooks ($\bar{X} = 3.62$, $SD = .80$), Handbooks ($\bar{X} = 3.51$, $SD = .78$), Manuals ($\bar{X} = 3.05$, $SD = .98$), Dictionaries ($\bar{X} = 3.11$, $SD = 1.10$), Magazine ($\bar{X} = 2.71$, $SD = 1.22$), Bibliography ($\bar{X} = 2.58$, $SD = 1.40$), Newspaper ($\bar{X} = 2.05$, $SD = 1.14$), Atlas and Maps ($\bar{X} = 1.77$, $SD = 1.12$), Encyclopedia ($\bar{X} = 1.75$, $SD = .89$) and Monographs ($\bar{X} = 1.26$, $SD = .66$). The Grand Mean and Standard Deviation of ($\bar{X} = 2.75$, $SD = .93$) indicate that agricultural scientists are aware of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state for improved research productivity. The finding of the study agrees with the finding of Eyiolorunshe and Eluwole (2017) who in their discovered that university staff are highly aware of information resources in the library. It agrees with the study of Kutu and Olajide (2020) who in their study revealed that there is high availability and utilization of information resources by academic staff in universities in North central Nigeria. The finding of this study is in line with Onifade, Ogbuiyi and Omeluzor (2013) who in their study found out that majority of the university students frequently utilized textbooks, monograph resources, Journals, handbooks, manuals, theses and dissertations among others for

research. The finding of this study corroborates with Ifijeh, Ogbomo and Ifijeh (2018) whose study discovered that university lecturers made use of the resources and the frequently used information resources are textbooks, journals, encyclopedia, newspapers/magazines, dictionaries, map, dictionary among. The finding of this study is in line with Hussaini, Vashitha and Jimah (2018) whose study also revealed that there is high level of awareness and utilization of information resources in the library and the frequently utilized information resources are textbooks/e-books, journals/e-journals, newspapers/magazines and internet/computers. The finding of this study agrees with Ilo, Igbashal and Agoh (2019) who in their study noted that the frequently utilized information resources are theses, dictionaries, manuals, textbooks, journals, handbooks among others. It also agrees with Ilo and Ozowa (2021) study who discovered that there is availability of information resources and agricultural scientists' are aware, accesses and utilizes the resources for research productivity.

Research Question Two

To what extent do agricultural scientists utilize agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state for improved research productivity?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the extent in which agricultural scientists utilize agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State for improved research productivity (N=133)

S/N	Item statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Rank	Decision
1	Textbooks	3.75	.66	2 nd	VHE
2	Journals	3.87	.43	1 st	VHE
3	Newspapers	2.88	1.23	9 th	HE
4	Magazine	1.88	.84	12 th	LE
5	Encyclopedia	3.48	.73	4 th	VHE
6	Handbooks	3.43	.95	5 th	VHE
7	Dictionaries	3.23	.90	6 th	VHE
8	Manuals	3.05	.98	7 th	VHE
9	Atlas and Maps	2.50	.82	10 th	HE
10	Theses and dissertations	3.70	.80	3 rd	VHE
11	Monographs	2.08	1.13	11 th	LE
12	Bibliography	2.99	.99	8 th	HE
Grand Mean and Decision		3.07	-		VHE

Result in Table 2 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation on the extent in which agricultural scientists utilize agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state for improved research productivity. The finding revealed Journals ($\bar{X} = 3.87$, SD = .43), Textbook ($\bar{X} = 3.75$, SD = .66), Theses and dissertation ($\bar{X} = 3.70$, SD = .80), Encyclopedia ($\bar{X} = 3.48$, SD = .73), Handbook ($\bar{X} = 3.43$, SD = .95), Dictionaries ($\bar{X} = 3.23$, SD = .90), Manuals ($\bar{X} = 3.05$, SD = .98), Bibliography ($\bar{X} = 2.99$, SD = .99), Newspaper ($\bar{X} = 2.88$, SD = 1.23), Atlas and Maps ($\bar{X} = 2.50$, SD = .82), Monographs ($\bar{X} = 2.08$, SD = 1.13) and Magazine ($\bar{X} = 1.88$, SD = .84). The Grand Mean and Standard Deviation of ($\bar{X} = 3.07$, SD = .87) indicate that agricultural scientists

utilize agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state for improved research productivity. The finding of this study is in line with the finding of Eyiolorunshe and Eluwole (2017) who found out that university staff utilized available print and electronic information resources for academic purposes. The finding of this study agrees with Song and Abbas (2019) who noted the availability and utilization of electronic information resources for research activities in agricultural research institutes. Their study also established that most of the information resources available are adequately utilized for research activities. The finding of this study is in line with the finding of Ilo, Igbashal and Agoh (2019) who in their study revealed that library information resources are available and are highly utilized for research productivity by agricultural scientists in agricultural institutions in Benue state. The finding of this study corroborates with Ilo and Ozowa (2021) who in their study noticed the availability of information resources and that, agricultural scientists accesses and utilizes the resources for research productivity.

Research Question Three

How does the utilization of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state improve the research productivity of agricultural scientists?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on how the utilization of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State improve the research productivity of agricultural scientists (N=133)

S/N	Item statement	Mean	Std Dev.	Rank	Decision
1	Information resources have helped to keep me updated on current information in the field of agriculture	3.58	.85	5 th	Agree
2	Information resources have helped me in carrying out my research effectively	3.80	.61	2 nd	Agree
3	Information resources have helped to improve in my article writing	3.95	.33	1 st	Agree
4	Information resources have helped to develop my ideas in the field of agriculture	3.75	.62	3 rd	Agree
5	Information resources have helped in staying up to date in current agricultural policies	3.74	.62	4 th	Agree
Grand Mean and Decision		3.76	-		Agree

Result in Table 3 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation on how the utilization of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state improve the research productivity of agricultural scientists. The finding revealed information resources have helped to improve in my article writing ($\bar{X} = 3.95$, $SD = .33$), information resources have helped me in carrying out my research effectively ($\bar{X} = 3.80$, $SD = .61$), information resources have helped to develop my ideas in the field of agriculture (\bar{X}

= 3.75, SD = .62), information resources have helped in staying up to date in current agricultural policies (\bar{X} = 3.74, SD = .62) and information resources have helped to keep me updated on current information in the field of agriculture (\bar{X} = 3.58, SD = .85). The Grand Mean and Standard Deviation of (\bar{X} = 3.76, SD = .61) indicate that the utilization of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state improve the research productivity of agricultural scientists. The finding of this study agrees with the finding of Ifijeh, Ogbomo and Ifijeh (2018) who noted that utilization of library resources improves lecturer research productivity. This study agrees with Zainab (2011) who in their study also discovered that researchers who utilized varied method to keep themselves up to date with current research literature are highly productive.

Research Question Four

What are the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity at?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation on the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity (N=133)

S/N	Item statement	Mean	Std Dev.	Rank	Decision
1	Poor access to internet	2.97	1.11	7 th	Agree
2	Busy schedule	3.40	.94	3 rd	Agree
3	Inadequate search skill	2.65	1.13	10 th	Agree
4	Inadequate information resources	3.24	.94	5 th	Agree
5	Management lukewarm attitude	3.29	1.00	4 th	Agree
6	Lack of current resources	3.62	.59	1 st	Agree
7	Inadequate library space	2.74	1.19	8 th	Agree
8	Inadequate loaning period	2.74	1.16	8 th	Agree
9	Constant power outage	3.43	.84	2 nd	Agree
10	Inadequate library skill	3.17	.94	6 th	Agree
Cluster Mean and Decision		3.03	-		Agree

Result in Table 4 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation on the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity. The finding revealed lack of current resources (\bar{X} = 3.62, SD = .59), constant power outage (\bar{X} = 3.43, SD = .84), busy schedule (\bar{X} = 3.40, SD = .94), management lukewarm attitude (\bar{X} = 3.29, SD = 1.00), inadequate information resources (\bar{X} = 3.24, SD = .94), inadequate library skill (\bar{X} = 3.17, SD = .94), poor access to internet (\bar{X} = 2.97, SD = 1.11), inadequate library space (\bar{X} = 2.74, SD = 1.19), inadequate loaning period (\bar{X} = 2.74, SD = 1.16) and inadequate search skill (\bar{X} = 2.65, SD = 1.13). The Grand Mean and

Standard Deviation of ($\bar{X} = 3.03$, $SD = .98$) indicate that agricultural scientists agreed that the items listed are the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity. This finding agrees with the finding of Onifade, Ogbuiyi and Omeluzor (2013) who revealed some of the challenges encountered in the utilization of information resources to include lack of time, insufficient internet access points, lack of library orientation, opening hours of the library, short duration of book loan, inadequate space in the library, obsolete books. The study is in line with Ifijeh, Ogbomo and Ifijeh (2018) who noted some of the challenges encountered by lecturers in the utilization of library resources to include cost of publication, time pressure and deadline, students project and theses supervision, delay in implementation of promotion and entitlement, excess workload, attendance to lectures and seminar, inadequate research personnel for instrumentality and analysis and so on. This study agrees with Zainab (2011) who discovered that inability to find relevant information and services, lack of information and not knowing how to choose relevant database are challenges encountered by researchers. This finding corroborates with the finding of Ilo and Ozowa (2021) who discovered irregular power supply, excessive library rules, poor network connectivity, inadequate relevant information resources in the library, poor indexing of information resources among others as challenges mostly encountered by agricultural scientists in agricultural institutions.

Research Question Five

What are solutions to the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity?

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of the solutions to the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue State in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity (N=133)

S/N	Item statement	Mean	Std Dev.	Rank	Decision
1	Creation of access to quality internet	3.02	1.14	8 th	Agree
2	Staff should create time for the utilization of information resources	3.33	1.06	3 rd	Agree
3	Training and retraining of staff	3.00	1.06	9 th	Agree
4	Provision of more agricultural information resources for staff	3.21	.98	4 th	Agree
5	Management should prioritize the provision of agricultural information resources	3.13	.98	7 th	Agree
6	Provision of current agricultural information resources	3.65	.70	1 st	Agree

7	The library should create more space for agricultural scientists to carry out their research activities	2.74	1.19	10 th	Agree
8	More period should be given to agricultural scientists who wants to borrow information resources	3.17	.96	5 th	Agree
9	Alternative power supply should be made available in the library	3.35	.85	2 nd	Agree
10	Training and retraining of library staff on the provision of agricultural information resources to agricultural scientists	3.15	1.17	6 th	Agree
Grand Mean and Decision		3.18	-		Agree

Result in Table 5 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the solutions to the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity. The finding revealed provision of current agricultural information resources ($\bar{X} = 3.65$, $SD = .70$), alternative power supply should be made available in the library ($\bar{X} = 3.35$, $SD = .85$), staff should create time for the utilization of information resources ($\bar{X} = 3.33$, $SD = 1.06$), Provision of more agricultural information resources for staff ($\bar{X} = 3.21$, $SD = .98$), more period should be given to agricultural scientists who wants to borrow information resources ($\bar{X} = 3.17$, $SD = .96$), training and retraining of library staff on the provision of agricultural information resources to agricultural scientists ($\bar{X} = 3.15$, $SD = 1.17$), management should prioritize the provision of agricultural information resources ($\bar{X} = 3.13$, $SD = .98$), creation of access to quality internet ($\bar{X} = 3.02$, $SD = 1.14$), training and retraining of staff ($\bar{X} = 3.00$, $SD = 1.06$) and the library should create more space for agricultural scientists to carry out their research activities ($\bar{X} = 2.74$, $SD = 1.19$). the Grand Mean and Standard Deviation of ($\bar{X} = 3.18$, $SD = 1.01$) indicate that agricultural scientists agreed that the items listed are the solutions to the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists at Francis Suleimanu Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state in the utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity. This finding is in line with the finding of Ifijeh, Ogbomo and Ifijeh (2018) whose study recommended that university management should ensure that required facility that ensure high level of utilization of library resources are adequately provided and work pressure should be reduced. The finding of this study agrees with Hussaini, Vashitha and Jimah (2018) who in their study recommended that institutions should provide vibrant library stacked with library resources updated to meet up the information requirement of library users. The finding of this study is in line with the finding of Ilo and Ozowa (2021) who recommended that if the challenges facing agricultural scientists in the utilization of information resources are tackled properly, it would go a long way in enhancing the research productivity of these agricultural scientists in agricultural institutions.

Conclusion

Based on this finding, it was concluded that agricultural scientists are aware of the agricultural information resources at Francis Suleiman Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state and these resources are utilized effectively for improved research productivity. There are numerous challenges encountered by agricultural scientists in the utilization of agricultural information resources at Francis Suleiman Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state for improved research productivity and if the solutions proffered are keyed into, the challenges encountered by agricultural scientists will be enhanced.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the study recommended that:

- i. The university management should provide more current resources and enough agricultural information resources at Francis Suleiman Idachaba Library Makurdi, Benue state to encourage more utilization of these resources by agricultural scientists for improved research productivity.
- ii. Francis Suleiman Idachaba Library should allocate more space for agricultural scientists to carry out their research activities and more loaning period also, should be given to agricultural scientists who wants to borrow information resources to encourage utilization of agricultural information resources for improved research productivity.
- iii. There should be training and retraining of both academic and library staff to create awareness and on how to access current agricultural information resources withing the library.

REFERENCES

- Aina, L. O. (2004). *Library and information science text for Africa*. Ibadan: Third world information services Limited.
- Amidu, G. & Akolo, S.D. (2015). Availability and use of information resources and services by students in Nasarawa State College of Agriculture Library, Lafia. *Jewel journal of Librarianship*. 9(1): 14-19.
- Eyiorunshe, T. A. & Eluwole, O. A. (2017). Awareness, accessibility and use of library resources by faculty members of Landmark University, Nigeria. *Information Impact Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 8(2), 118-124.
- Hanif, U., Zabed, S. M. & Nasir, U. M (2007). Adequacy of reading resources and the satisfaction needs of the faculty members: A case study of Dhaka University Library. Retrieved april, 2017, from <http://infosciencetoday.org>
- Hussaini, S., Vashistha, R. & Jimah, H. (2018). Awareness and utilization of library resources by library users' of Nims University Central Library, Jaipur, India. *International Journal of Movement Education and Social Science*, 7(2): 1067-1078. Retrieved 28/1/2020 from <https://sg.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/219224/22/22%20published%20paper%202.pdf>

- Ifijeh, B. A., Ogbomo, M. O. & Ifijeh, G. (2018). Utilization of academic library resources for research productivity among lecturers in private universities in South-South Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, pp 1-23 Retrieved online 10/7/2022 from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/162044084.pdf>
- Ilo, H. M. & Ozowa, V. (2021). Availability and tilization of information resources by agricultural scientists for research productivity in agricultural institutions in Benue State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Information Practice and Management (IJIPM)*, 1(1): 129-143
- Ilo, H. M., Agoh, J. A. & Igbashal, A. A. (2019). Influence of library information resources and services on research productivity of agricultural scientists in agricultural institutions in Benue State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. Retrieved 28/1/2020 from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/3874/>
- kutu, J. O. & Olajide, O. (2020). Information resources availability, utilization and job and performance of academic librarians in selected university libraries in North Central Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 1-29. Retrieved online 10/7/2022 from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=7602&context=libphilprac>
- Maidabino, A. A., & Ladan, A. (2015). Library carnival as a strategy for promoting university library services in Nigeria: a model of what to do and how to do it. *Jewel Journal of Librarianship* Gombe State Chapter, 1-8.
- Okiki, O. C. (2013). Availability of information resources for research output: Perception of academic staff members in Nigerian Federal Universities. *International Journal of Computer Science and Telecommunication*, 4(8), 26-33.
- Onifade, F. N., Ogbuiyi, S. U. & Omeluzor, S. U. (2013). Library resources and service utilization by postgraduate students in a Nigerian private university. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 5(9), 289-294.
- Song, U. M. & Abas, K. D. (2019). Availability and utilization of electronic information resources for research activities in agricultural research institutes in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Journal of ICT Development, Applications and Research*, (1), 33 – 46.
- Suleiman, H., Vashistha, R. & Jimah, H. (2018). Awareness and utilization of library resources by library users' of NIMS university central library, Jaipur, India. *International Journal of Movement Education and Social Sciences*, 7(2), 1067-1078.
- Uganneya, S., Ape, R. & Ugbagir, N. (2013). Factors inhibiting the performance of agricultural Research Libraries and Information Services in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 923.
- Zainab, A.N. (2011). Library resources and services and publication productivity. *Malaysian Journal of Library and Information Science*, 6 (1): 71-91